

Research Paper

The Devil Behind the Scene: A Critical Review of the Richards Constitution of 1946

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ABSTRACT: This paper “The Devil behind the Scene: A Critical Review of the Richards Constitution of 1946” argues that the Richards Constitution is the bane of contemporary Nigerian problems. In the quest for knowing the problems of Nigeria, some scholars and opinion leaders such as Chinua Achebe, Wole Soyinka, and Obafemi Awolowo and others stated that the problem with Nigeria is leadership, while others stated that ethnicity, religious differences, disunity and favouritism are the embodiment of Nigeria’s problems. Hence, no adequate information concerning the root cause of the aforementioned problems is provided. This paper argues that the Richards Constitution of 1946, is the root cause of the problems listed above. The work is descriptive and analytical. Data is collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources consulted are correspondences such as official letters and statements. On the other hand, the secondary sources used are books, articles in journals, chapters in books, newspapers and magazines. The paper adopts Colonial and Divide-and-Rule Theories as analytical tools to reveal the hidden ambition of the British colonial government in the introduction of the said constitution of 1946. From the work, it is discovered that the Richards Constitution of 1946, is a chronic instigator of contemporary Nigerian problems.

I.

Introduction

There is no nation or state that is problem free. Every nation has a problem that it is battling with. As nations or states varies, so are their problems. The problem of Nigeria is multifaceted. Some scholars point it to leadership failure, while others state that the problem with Nigeria is lack of unity occasioned by ethnic differences. These set of people believed that ethnic differences ignited nepotism, tribalism, selfishness and inter-ethnic conflicts. They also believed that the various political crises such as the federal election crises of 1964, western election crises of 1965 and the subsequent coups and counter coups in the 1960s to 1980s were caused by ethnic differences based on power tussle and dominance (Coleman, 1958). However, the fact is that Nigeria is made up of over three-hundred and fifty (350) ethnic groups (Eberhard *etal*,2025). Consequently, the people hardly understood themselves in terms of unity and administrative purposes. According to Oladele Fadeye (2012), Nigeria is a British creation, and that there was nothing like Nigeria until 1914, when the northern and southern protectorates were amalgamated. In the same vein, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa (1948) opined that, “since 1914, the British Government has been trying to make

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Nigeria into one country, but the Nigerian people themselves are historically different in their backgrounds, in their religious beliefs and customs and do not show themselves any sign of willingness to unite... Nigerian unity is only a British intention for the country". While this issue of ethnicity was gaining momentum, Chinua Achebe (1983) wrote "there is nothing wrong with the Nigerian environment. The only problem with Nigeria is leadership".

On his part, J.P. Clark (2000) attributed the problems of Nigeria to British creation. In his work, *All for Oil*, Clark argues that the colonial masters destroyed the indigenous practices of the local people while exploiting the rich economic resources. In the same vein, Chinua Achebe (1958) argues in *Things Fall Apart* that the white man (colonial masters) destroyed the unity of the indigenous people. He said: "we foolishly allowed the Whiteman and followed him. Now, he has put knife on things that joined us together". Chinua Achebe and J.P Clark attributed the lack of unity in Nigeria to colonial creation. However, behind all the Nigerian problems enumerated above, the Richards Constitution of 1946, is a chronic instigator, the devil behind the scene of the problems encountered by Nigerians but this has not been adequately explained or captured in historical and scientific scholarships. Hence, this paper argues that the current Nigerian problems are caused by the Richards Constitution of 1946. The paper adopted Colonial Theory as its primary analytical framework, and complemented it with the Divide-and-Rule Theory to interrogate the hidden motives, power structures and the political consequences of the Richards Constitution of 1946.

II. The Arthur Richards Constitution of 1946

Before the Richards Constitution came into existence, the country (Nigeria) was engulfed with political crisis. This was because political consciousness and awareness was on the rise. The colonial government deemed it necessary to provide a working constitution or document to rule the newly created state (Nigeria). Consequently, the Nigerian council was constituted by Fredrick Lord Lugard, the first colonial governor immediately after the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern protectorates in 1914. The council was made up of a governor, two lieutenant governors, and administrator of the Colony of Lagos, and an executive council (Ibiyemi O. *etal*, 2002). It also included thirty-six (36) members consisting of twenty-three European officials and thirteen non-official members. Out of the thirteen non-official members, seven were Europeans and six Nigerians. The seven European non official members represented business interests such as commerce, shipping, banking and mining. The six Nigerian non-official members were illiterates. They were chosen to represent chieftaincy and traditional interests. (Ibiyemi *etal*, 2002). The council's meetings were irregular, attendance was not impressive and above all, it has no power to make decisions. It was purely an advisory body. (Ibiyemi *etal*, 2002). According to Okafor L.M (2004), the council had no legislative or executive powers. It could only discuss issues and make recommendations which the Governor was not ready to accept.

Based on the weaknesses of the council, Nigerians protested and equally asked for constitutional reforms. Coupled with the above and aggravated political tensions in the country, were the various colonial policies that restricted Nigerians from working in the colonial government. These policies according to Claude Ake (1984) included racial discrimination, the indirect rule system and the appointment policy. Under the appointment policy, Nigerians were appointed rather than elected into advisory councils ensuring loyalty to colonial interests and limiting independent political influence. To over-ride this, Nigerians kicked against these policies especially discrimination. The displeasure or dissatisfaction expressed by Nigerians over colonial tendencies was so intense that adjustment was to be made. Therefore, when Sir Hugh Clifford became the Governor General of Nigeria after the death of Sir Fredrick Lord Lugard in 1919, he made wide consultations on the political affairs of the country and in 1922, abolished the Nigerian Council and introduced a working constitution that enabled Nigerians to hold elective positions. According to Ibiyemi *etal* (2002), the Sir Hugh Clifford's Constitution of 1922 was a response to the demands of the National Congress of British West Africa (NCBWA). The congress demanded for elective principles in West Africa in which the constitution also captured. The Clifford Constitution provided an executive council for the whole country. It also had a legislative council which was composed of forty-six members, twenty-seven including the governor were Europeans (British) and they were called official members. The remaining nineteen members were non-official, out of whom were ten Nigerians including three elected to represent Lagos and one to represent Calabar. The constitution allowed only male adults who earned up to one-hundred pounds per annum and had resided in the area for at least a year to vote during elections as revealed by Ibiyemi *etal* (2002).

The constitution looked fascinating in the eyes of Nigerians as it gave them the opportunity for the very first time to vote for their representatives and to have a voice in national affairs. In response, political

parties were founded by Nigerians to contest for elective positions. The Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) was founded by Sir Herbert Macaulay. The party won all the three seats allocated to Lagos in 1923, 1928 and 1933 (Okafor, 2004). Other political parties that emerged during the period include the Nigerian Youth Movement (NYM) and the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC). Both the NCNC and the NYM emerged as protestant or nationalist groups, but was later converted to political parties (Okafor 2004).

Despite the fact that the Clifford Constitution of 1922 provided the elective principle to aid Nigerians participation in politics and to have a voice in national affairs, the constitution was later criticized on the grounds that it vested too much power in the governor and it also isolated the north from the south thereby creating north and south dichotomy. The constitution was also criticized because it disenfranchised many Nigerians by limiting voting rights to only adult males earning at least one-hundred pounds per annum (Ezera, 1960). The defects of the Clifford Constitution were highly pronounced and it served as an effective instrument for the nationalists in their quest for self-rule hence, leading to further introduction of a new working constitution, thus, the Richards Constitution of 1946 came into being.

As stated above, the Richards Constitution of 1946 came into existence as a result of the weaknesses of the Clifford Constitution of 1922, which was largely criticized by the nationalists. Bernard Bourdillon, the Governor of Nigeria between 1935 and 1943, who succeeded Sir Hugh Clifford created room for a new constitution. He appealed to the northern leaders to join the southern leaders in the legislative council in Lagos. However, he could not achieve his plan because he left the country unexpectedly. It was his successor, Arthur Richards who continued the work and presented a new constitution in 1946, which took effect from January, 1947(Okafor, 2004).

The aim of the Richards Constitution of 1946, was to promote the unity of Nigeria while it acknowledged the country's diverse socio-cultural, economic and regional differences and broaden Nigerians participation in governance and to provide a constitutional framework that will further strengthen British control of the country. The objectives of the Richards Constitution of 1946 are as follows: To strengthen Nigeria's unity, develop a constitution that encompasses the entire country, split the country into three regions-North, West, and East-and establish regional councils for each; increase Nigerians' involvement in their own affairs and governance; and establish a legislative council that will represent the entire nation. (Ibiyemi *etal* 2002).

III. Features of the Richards Constitution of 1946

Okafor (2004) and Ibiyemi *etal* (2002) highlighted the features of the Richards Constitution of 1946 as follows:

- The constitution established a central legislative council for the whole of the country (Nigeria)
- The constitution divided Nigeria into three regions-North, West and East
- The constitution established regional assemblies in the North, East and West, but the assemblies were limited in making laws. They only discussed legislations and act as electoral colleges for the election of legislative council members. (Ibiyemi *etal* 2002).
- The northern region had a bicameral legislature consisting of a house of chiefs and a house of assembly, according to the constitution, whereas the eastern and western regions had a unicameral legislature consisting of a house of assembly. The majority of the regional assemblies' representatives—eighteen officials and twenty-four non-officials in the north, thirteen officials and nineteen non-officials in the west, and thirteen officials and eighteen non-officials in the east—were chosen by local authorities. (Ibiyemi *etal*, 2002).

In the West and the East, the Chief Commissioner was the president of the house of assembly, whereas in the North, the Chief Commissioner oversaw the house of chiefs and left the house of assembly to the senior resident. Although they were not permitted to pass laws, the legislative council in Lagos sent laws that were pertinent to or applicable to the regional houses for discussion and, if needed, to offer comments or advice. Additionally, the governor has the power to reject these suggestions. Okafor (2004). The governor could not act contrary to the decisions or recommendations of the legislative council without the approval of the colonies' secretary of state (Okafor, 2004).

Additionally, the legislative council was expanded under the constitution. With sixteen minority officials and twenty-eight majority non-officials, the council now numbered forty-four. The twenty-eight non-officials included four elected members from Lagos and Calabar, as well as nine, six, and five nominations representing corporate interests. Thirteen of the sixteen members were ex-officio, while three were nominated.

IV. A Critical Review of the Richards Constitution of 1946

The Richards Constitution of 1946, was first of its kind in the history of constitutional development in Nigeria. As earlier noted, the aim of the constitution was to promote the unity of Nigeria. The governor (Richards) acknowledged the fact that Nigeria is not a homogenous country as it embodies people of different ethnic, cultural and religious backgrounds. Hence, through the constitution, the governor divided the country into three regions – North, East and West. According to Sunday Gabriel (1995), one of the chronic defects of the Richards Constitution was the non-consultation of Nigerians. Richards introduced the constitution without consulting Nigerians, consequently, the constitution did not address the prevailing circumstances of the Nigeria people, and in effect, compounded Nigeria's problems. The division of the country into three regions ignited regional consciousness. The people began to see themselves as different people and not as one. The introduction of the Richards Constitution of 1946, was the beginning of the balkanization of Nigeria. The country became factionalized and polarized. The regions began to struggle for political power rather than the unity and development of the country. This is evident in the philosophies of the first political parties that emerged. For instance, the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC) later, National Council of Nigerian Citizens, headed by Nnamdi Azikiwe was kin to protecting the interest of the eastern region. The Action Group, led by Chief Obafemi Awolowo was for the interest of the western region, while the northern region responded with the Northern People's Congress (NPC). Thus, the parties were regionally aligned leading to ethnic and regional sentiments. This situation persists till now as ethnicity, nepotism, favouritism and others, constitutes part of the Nigeria's problems.

The division of the country into three regions equally spelt out the religious differences, beliefs and practices of the Nigerian people. The Northern region was and till date dominated by the Islamic religion, while the Western and Eastern regions were and up till now dominated by the Christian religion (Christianity). The doctrines of these religions are different and so are the adherents. Northerners are often called Muslims while the Westerners and the Easterners are called Christians. Base on religious differences, there is a dichotomy between the Northern region and the Western and Eastern regions. These religious differences persist till date, as it is one of the biggest Nigerian problems.

The Northerners had Islamic education as early as the 8th century, while the Westerners and the Easterners had western education during the 15th century (Basil Davidson, 1966). However, studies have shown that western education is one of the causes of the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria. According to Thurston A. (2017) Boko Haram opposes what it perceived as western secular education. To the Boko Haram leaders, Western education is a forbidden practice. They argued that western education promotes secularism, undermines Islamic values and encourages moral corruption. These were underlining philosophies and ideologies of Boko Haram leaders (Thurston, 2017). They, therefore, seized the opportunity to mobilize followers and use it as a propaganda against Christian practices. The fact is that Islam as a religion was gathering momentum in Nigeria and if the British had not come to Nigeria, Nigeria would have been an Islamic country. Therefore, the arrival of the British was an antidote to the massive spread of Islamic culture in Nigeria. Thus, Nigeria is a secular country with two major religions: Christianity and Islam.

Another critical aspect of the Richards Constitution of 1946, was the creation of regional imbalances which resulted to political domination in today's Nigerian politics. The constitution provided for a bicameral legislature of two chambers of a house of chiefs and a house of assembly in the Northern region while the Eastern and Western regions had a unicameral legislature: a house of assembly each. Therefore, the Northern region enjoyed greater representation than the eastern and western regions. This political imbalance created by the Richards Constitution of 1946, still persist till date. The Northerners are still dominating the politics of Nigeria. To this, it is felt that they are the dictators of Nigerian politics. This is mostly attributed to their numerical strength and their influence in the First and Second Republics. During the First Republic, the Northern People's Congress (NPC) dominated national politics because of the North's numerical strength. Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa was the Prime Minister, Sir Ahmadu Bello, the Sarkin Sokoto was the Premier of the Northern region. Apart from that, he was also a dominant political figure in national affairs. Other prominent offices held by Northerners in the First Republic include the various ministries such as the Ministry of Defense, Internal Affairs and Finance. Alhaji Muhammadu Ribadu was the Minister of Defense. He was one of the most powerful ministers of the First Republic and played a key role in security and federal administration.

The second Republic operated a presidential system of government and once again, a Northerner, Alhaji Shehu Shagari became the first executive president of Nigeria. All these attests to the fact that Northerners are dominating Nigerian politics as made possible by the Richards Constitution of 1946. This dominance fueled regional distrust and political tension which shaped Nigeria's post-independence political history.

The Richards Constitution of 1946, is also responsible for the outbreak of the Nigerian Civil War in 1967. As rightly observed by Armstrong (2008), there was a regional sentiment and power domination in the country. If Yakubu Gowon had been an Igbo from the eastern region, there wouldn't have been a war in the country. Ojukwu's refusal to accept Gowon as the new head of state was not born out of military seniority only as it had strong ethnic inclination. The east was determined to hold on to power at the centre which would have made it a dominant region in Nigeria's politics, while the north perceived the east (Igbos) as a threat to their political ambition. This was made clear during the first military coup of January, 15th, 1966. Majority of the coup plotters were from the east led by Nzeokwu, while the casualties were mostly felt in the north. The Prime Minister, Alhaji Tafawa Balewa, and the then Sardauna of Sokoto, Ahmadu Bello all from the north lost their lives during the coup. The northerners felt that the coup was a calculated attempt by the easterners to wipe out their top political and military officers with the aim of controlling Nigeria's political scene. Thus, north and east dichotomy was created. The result was the outcome of the July, counter coup initiated by the northerners to seize power from the east. Thus, bringing to power Yakubu Gowon as the new Head of State. Coupled with the above was the killing of the Igbos in the north hence, Ojukwu decided to break the east out of Nigeria thereby declaring the east, Biafra Republic in 1967. The Nigerian military government responded with what was termed as "a police action" which brought about the Nigerian civil war. Till date, the north opposes the east from holding the position of a President in Nigeria's politics.

In another dimension, the constitution concentrated too much power on the Governor. The Governor retained extensive powers including veto authority and control over the executive council. This also surfaced in today's Nigerian constitution. Though, Nigerians had their own constitution during independence but the colonial element is still in the constitution since the first republic. From this research, it was discovered that Nigerians are still operating a colonial constitution especially the Richards Constitution of 1946. What they did was just an amendment of the Richards Constitution wherein major features of the constitution are still retained. Currently, the Nigerian constitution is one of the biggest problems of Nigeria. It concentrated too much power on the President. Eighty percent (80%) of the President's functions are in the exclusive list, implying that it is only the President that have powers to legislate on those items, thereby restricting other arms of government and government functionaries from legislating or acting on them, while the concurrent list constitutes only 20% of Governors' functions by which the President can also exercise powers. In essence, 90% of the powers in the constitution is vested on the president (1999 Constitution as Amended). To this, it is the responsibility of the President to nominate Ministers, Ambassadors, the Chairman of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) and the Chief Justice of the Federation subject to Senate Screening and approval. However, it is always very difficult to reject such nominees from the President (Ezera, 1960). It, therefore, suffice to say that the powers of the President cannot be challenged hence, in theory Nigeria is a democratic state but in practice, Nigeria is a semi-military state. The President is the Commander-in-Chief-of-the-Armed-Forces of –the- Federal Republic of Nigeria. This means that he has control over the Military, the Police, and Civil Defense and among other forces including paramilitaries in the country. Until the constitution is revisited and amended to curtail the powers of the President and expunge the colonial elements, Nigeria will still be "bleeding"

V. **Theoretical Analysis**

As earlier stated in the introduction, the paper adopted two theories: Colonial and Divide-and-Rule Theories. The Colonial Theory examines how colonial powers designated political institutions to protect imperial ambitions/interests rather than the welfare or political aspirations of the colonized people. The theory emerged during the 15th century when European powers ventured into the third world nations in search of territories which was characterized by economic, political and social factors. Developers of this theory include Karl Marx, Frederick Engel, Vladimir Lenin, Frantz Fanon and Edward Sad. Karl Mark and Frederick Engel (1846) scrutinized colonialism from an economic perspective. According to them, colonial expansion was characterized by the development of capitalism in Europe. Accordingly, they remarked that

European capitalist states-Britain, Germany, France, Spain, Belgium and Portugal needed raw materials, markets and cheap labour which ushered them to conquer and control foreign territories. They went further to argue that colonialism allowed the capitalist countries to accumulate wealth by exploiting the resources of the colonized territories.

In his credible work *Imperialism, the Highest Stage of Capitalism* Lenin (1917) argued that colonialism was a direct result of advanced capitalism. He went further to say that with the rise of capitalism in Europe which was aided by the industrial revolution, large corporations and financial institutions sought new markets and investment opportunities abroad. This economic pressure according to him pushed powerful nations to subjugate weaker ones, consequently, the wealth of colonized countries was transferred to industrial powers.

Fanon (1961) in his work *The Wretched of the Earth* analyzed the psychological and cultural effects of colonial domination. Edward Said (1978) contributed to colonial theory through his *Orientalism*. He stated that colonial domination was reinforced through knowledge and cultural representation. According to him, western scholars and writers often labelled eastern societies as backward, irrational and inferior thereby giving justification to colonial rule. This system of representation which he called *orientalism* helped to legitimize European domination by presenting colonialism as a civilizing mission. However, in view of the colonial theory, the Richards Constitution of 1946, was introduced to fulfill colonial requirements to enable the British government to have an absolute control of the territory without a strong and united opposition from the locals. This is why the constitution divided the country into three regions: West, East and North, the aim was to kill the unity of the local people especially the nationalists so that they could not speak in one voice in national affairs.

In another dimension, the constitution was introduced without the consent or consultation of Nigerians. Hence, this reflected the authoritarian nature of colonial powers- political monopoly. As a result, decision-making power remained firmly in the hand of the Governor who had veto powers over legislation.

On the other hand, Divide-and-Rule Theory (*divide et impera*) is a strong political strategy whereby a ruling power maintains control by creating or encouraging divisions among subordinate groups. The aim is to prevent them from uniting against the authority (Cowder 1968). The theory has its root in ancient political thought but became more pronounced in the colonial era particularly in Africa and Asia. Proponents of this theory include Nicolo Machiavelli (1469-1527), Julius Caesar(100-44BC) and Lord Milner (1854-1925). In his famous work, *The Prince*, Nicolo Machiavelli encouraged rulers to maintain power by managing rivalries and preventing unity among subjects. The theory was also used by Julius Caesar. The Latin expression *divide et impera* (divide and rule) is commonly associated with the Roman political practice. During his reign, Caesar applied the strategy by encouraging divisions among conquered territories to make them easier to govern. This is the case of the Richards Constitution of 1946. The division of the country into three regions was to prevent a unified force of resistance mostly from the nationalists. Through this division, the people saw themselves as different set of people rather than Nigerians. They began to struggle for regional domination and power. The constitution provided two legislative chambers in the north: a house of assembly and a house of chiefs, while the west and east only one chamber, a house of assembly. The aim of this was to weaken the strength of the west and east where there were powerful and vocal nationalists such as Nnamdi Azikiwe, Obafemi Awolowo, Ernest Ikoli, Anthony Enahoro, Michael Okpara, and among others. The political imbalance created by the constitution fostered regional rivalry rather than national unity or cooperation.

VI. Conclusion

From the theories analyzed above, the Richards Constitution of 1946, was a calculated effort to preserve British domination in Nigeria. The constitution polarized the country just to entrench division, limit popular participation and to preserve colonial control. In doing that, the constitution instigated disunity, intimidation and hatred among Nigerian citizens, hence, Nigeria is a divided country with people of different ethnic, religious, cultural and regional backgrounds. Unity is required for national development. This is what necessitated the popular saying that “united we stand, divided we fall”. Nigeria is falling and failing. She needs recreation. The introduction of the Richards Constitution of 1946, was the beginning of Nigeria’s decapitation, hence, this paper argues that Nigerians’ contemporary problems are British creations. Until the blood of Europeanism/Colonialism is drilled out of Nigerians, and they begin to see themselves as one, irrespective of their social, economic, political and cultural differences, no amounts of interventions can solve Nigerian problems.

References

- 1) Achebe, C (1958), *Things Fall Apart*. Ibadan: Heinemann.
- 2) Achebe, C (1983) *The problem with Nigeria*. Lagos: Heinemann Educational Books.
- 3) Afigbo, A.E. (1980), “The Eastern Province under Colonial Rule” in Obaro 1. (ed) *Groundwork of Nigerian History*. Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books.
- 4) Ake, C. (1984), *Political Economy of Africa*. Ibadan: University of Ibadan Press
- 5) Armstrong, M.A (2008), *The Nigeria Civil War: Forty Years after, What Lessons?* Benue: Aboki Publishers.
- 6) Awolowo, O. (1947), *Path to Nigerian Freedom*. London: Faber & Faber.
- 7) Balewa, A.T. (1948), *Speech in the Legislative Council in Legislative Council Debates*. Lagos: Government Printer.
- 8) Basil, D (1981), *A History of West Africa 1000-1800*. London: Longman.
- 9) Clark, J.P. (2000), *All for Oil*. Ibadan: University of Ibadan Press.
- 10) Coleman, J.S. (1958), *Nigeria: Background to Nationalism*. USA: University of California Press.
- 11) Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999). Lagos: Government Printer.
- 12) Crowder, M. (1962), *The Story of Nigeria*. London: Faber & Faber.
- 13) Crowder, M. (1978), *West Africa under Colonial Rule*. London: Hutchinson.
- 14) Dudley, B.J. (1973), *Instability and Political Order: Politics and Crisis in Nigeria*. Ibadan: University of Ibadan Press.
- 15) Ezera, K. (1960), *Constitutional Development in Nigeria: An Analytical Study of Nigerian Constitutional Law, 1914 – 1960*. UK: Cambridge University Press.
- 16) Fawole, W. A (2003), *Nigeria’s External Relations and Foreign Policy under Military Rule (1966-1999)*. Ile-Ife: Obafemi Awolowo University Press Ltd.
- 17) Ibiyemi O. *etal* (2002), *Round-up Government*. Lagos: Longman Nigeria Plc.
- 18) Lenin, V. I. (1917), *Imperialism: The Highest Stage of Capitalism*. Petrograd: Pravda Publishing Houses
- 19) Loimeier, R. (2012), “Boko Haram: The Development of a Militant Religious Movement in Nigeria”. *Africa Spectrum*, 47(2-3), 137-155.
- 20) Marx K & Engel F. (1932), *The German Ideology*. International Publishers. Moscow: Progress Publishers.
- 21) Obi, E. A. (2005), *Political Economy of Nigeria*. Onitsha: Book Point Ltd.
- 22) Obikeze, O.S A. and Obi, E. A (2003), *Nigerian Government and Politics: The Struggle for Power in an African State*. Onitsha: Book Point Ltd.
- 23) Okafor, L.M. (2004), *History for Senior Secondary Schools*, Books 1 & 2. Onitsha: Jet Publishers.
- 24) Oladele F. (2012), *Groundwork Essays on European Conquest and African Resistance*. Ibadan: Sterlin-Horden Publishers Ltd.
- 25) Perouse de Montclos, M. A. (2014), *Boko Haram: Islamism, Politics, Security and the State in Nigeria*. Boston University: African Studies Centre.
- 26) Schwarz F. (1965), *Nigeria: The Tribe, the Nation or the Race*. Cambridge: M.I.T. Press.
- 27) Sklar, R. L. (1963), *Nigerian Political Parties: Power in an Emergent African Nation*. Lagos: Nok Publishers International.
- 28) Thurston, A. (2017), *Boko Haram the History of African Jihadist Movement*. New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- 29) Walker, A. (2012), *What is Boko Haram?* United States Institution of Peace. Washington, D.C., USA